

COMPARISON OF MATERNAL SERUM MAGNESIUM LEVEL IN PREECLAMPSIA AND NORMAL PREGNANT WOMEN

Dr. Rabia Pervaiz^{*1}, Prof. Dr. Nuzhat Parveen Khawaja²

¹Post Graduate Trainee, Obstetrics & Gynecology, National Hospital & Medical Center, Lahore

²Professor, Obstetrics & Gynecology, National Hospital & Medical Center, Lahore

¹rabiash Sheikh3344@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17383739>

Keywords

Pre-eclampsia, Serum magnesium, Pregnancy, Blood pressure, Maternal health

Article History

Received: 18 July 2025

Accepted: 21 July 2025

Published: 26 August 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Rabia Pervaiz

Abstract

Objective: To compare serum magnesium levels between women with pre-eclampsia and with normal pregnancies, and evaluate the relationship between magnesium levels and blood pressure.

Study Design: Comparative Cross-sectional study

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, National Hospital and Medical Centre, Lahore, in 6 months.

Methodology: The study involved a total of 60 pregnant women attending antenatal care, 30 women with clinically diagnosed pre-eclampsia and 30 with uncomplicated pregnancies. Serum magnesium levels were measured using the colorimetric xylin blue method on an automated biochemical analyzer, and blood pressure was recorded using a standardized protocol.

Results: Women with pre-eclampsia had lower serum magnesium levels (1.72 ± 0.19 mg/dL) than those with normal pregnancies (2.05 ± 0.21 mg/dL, $p < 0.001$). They also had higher systolic (152.5 ± 11.6 mmHg) and diastolic blood pressures (101.7 ± 7.8 mmHg) compared to controls (112.8 ± 8.2 mmHg and 73.4 ± 5.1 mmHg, respectively; $p < 0.001$). A moderate negative correlation was found between serum magnesium and both systolic ($r = -0.61$, $p < 0.01$) and diastolic BP ($r = -0.57$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting reduced magnesium may play a role in preeclampsia.

Conclusion: Reduced serum magnesium levels are significantly associated with pre-eclampsia and correlate inversely with blood pressure. Routine monitoring of magnesium during pregnancy may aid in early detection and prevention strategies for pre-eclampsia.

INTRODUCTION

Pre-eclampsia is a multisystem disorder of pregnancy characterized by new-onset hypertension (systolic ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic ≥ 90 mmHg) after 20 weeks of gestation, often accompanied by proteinuria or organ dysfunction. Its global prevalence ranges from 5% to 7%, contributing significantly to maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in low- and middle-income countries¹. While delivery of

the fetus and placenta is the definitive treatment, early detection and supportive management are essential². Its pathogenesis is multifactorial, involving abnormal placentation, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and immune maladaptation³. Nutritional deficiencies, particularly in minerals like calcium, magnesium, and zinc, have been implicated⁴.

Magnesium, a cofactor in over 300 enzymatic reactions, is vital for energy metabolism, nucleic acid synthesis, and neuromuscular function⁵. It has modest blood pressure-lowering effects and supports cardiovascular health⁶.

Observational studies report lower serum magnesium in preeclamptic women compared to normotensive controls. One cross-sectional study found significantly reduced levels (1.72 ± 0.38 mg/dL vs. 2.2 ± 0.63 mg/dL; $p < 0.05$)⁴, and a case-control study reported post-diagnosis magnesium levels of 0.53 ± 0.06 mmol/L in cases versus 0.69 ± 0.08 mmol/L in controls ($p < 0.001$)⁷. Meta-analyses confirm these associations, with a pooled SMD of -1.20 (95% CI: -1.64 to -0.75)⁸ and a global weighted mean difference of -0.215 mg/dL ($p < 0.01$)⁶.

Mechanistically, magnesium induces vasodilation, inhibits platelet aggregation, and modulates vascular reactivity, suggesting that hypomagnesemia could aggravate endothelial dysfunction⁹. Magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄) remains the gold standard for seizure prophylaxis in pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, reducing eclampsia risk by over 50% without increasing perinatal harm^{10,11}.

Lower serum magnesium in early gestation may predict pre-eclampsia^{1,12} and supplementation may improve maternal and neonatal outcomes, though evidence is not yet conclusive⁶. Variations in findings likely reflect differences in diet, populations, methodology, and timing of sampling^{4,9}. Further prospective studies are required to clarify causality.

Aim of the Present Study

This study aims to investigate maternal serum magnesium levels in preeclamptic versus

normotensive pregnant women. It seeks to elucidate the role of serum magnesium as a reliable marker for pre-eclampsia and inform early intervention strategies to improve maternal-fetal outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a comparative cross-sectional quantitative design to examine and compare the maternal serum magnesium levels in women diagnosed with pre-eclampsia and those with normal pregnancies.

Study Sampling

The study population consisted of pregnant women attending antenatal care at the selected hospital. Two groups were defined:

1. **Pre-eclampsia group** (30 Patients) – women clinically diagnosed with pre-eclampsia based on elevated blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$ mmHg) after 20 weeks of gestation and presence of proteinuria.

2. **Normal pregnancy group** (30 Patients) – women with no signs of pre-eclampsia, normal blood pressure, and absence of proteinuria.

A purposive sampling method was used to recruit participants meeting the inclusion criteria. The sample size was calculated using a power analysis to ensure adequate statistical significance, with equal representation from both groups.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria Inclusion criteria included:

- Pregnant women aged 18–40 years
- Gestational age ≥ 30 weeks
- Willingness to provide informed consent
- diabetes before pregnancy
- Current magnesium supplementation
- Renal or liver disease
- Multiple pregnancies

Exclusion criteria included:

- History of chronic hypertension or

Study Duration: 6 Months

Data Collection Procedure

Data collection involved two components:

1. **Clinical assessment** - blood pressure measurement, urinalysis for proteinuria, and demographic/obstetric data through structured interviews.
2. **Laboratory analysis** - venous blood samples (5 mL) were collected under aseptic conditions. Serum was separated via centrifugation and stored at -20°C until analysis. Magnesium levels were measured using the colourimetric xylidyl blue method on an automated biochemical analyzer.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into SPSS software for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions, were computed for demographic and clinical variables. An **independent samples t-test** was used to compare serum magnesium levels between the pre-eclampsia group and the normal pregnancy group. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board of the participating

hospital. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality of data was maintained. Blood sampling was performed following standard biosafety protocols, and participation was voluntary with the option to withdraw at any stage. (NHMC/EXP/IRB/151)

RESULTS

The age distribution across both groups was similar, with the majority of participants aged 26–30 years, suggesting that age is not a potential confounding factor as shown in table 1. A significant difference in serum magnesium levels was observed, with the pre-eclampsia group having lower levels (1.72 ± 0.19 mg/dL) compared to the normal pregnancy group (2.05 ± 0.21 mg/dL), and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) as shown in Table 2. The pre-eclampsia group exhibited markedly higher blood pressure, with average systolic (152.5 ± 11.6 mmHg) and diastolic (101.7 ± 7.8 mmHg) pressures, compared to the normal pregnancy group, which had systolic (112.8 ± 8.2 mmHg) and diastolic (73.4 ± 5.1 mmHg) pressures ($p < 0.001$). In the pre-eclampsia group, a significant negative correlation was found between serum magnesium levels and blood pressure, with correlation coefficients of $r = -0.61$ (systolic) and $r = -0.57$ (diastolic),

Table 1. Participants Distribution

Variable	Normal Pregnancy (n = 30)	Pre-Eclampsia (n = 30)	p-value
Age (years, Mean ± SD)	27.1 ± 4.5	27.8 ± 4.8	0.58
Gestational Age (weeks)	36.5 ± 1.9	35.8 ± 2.2	0.14
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.6 ± 3.2	26.8 ± 3.5	0.18
Primigravida (%)	40%	43%	0.79

Table 2. Serum Magnesium Levels in Both Groups

Group	Serum Magnesium (mg/dL, Mean ± SD)	95% CI	p-value
Normal Pregnancy	2.05 ± 0.21	2.00 – 2.12	
Pre-Eclampsia	1.72 ± 0.19	1.66 – 1.78	<0.001

Table 3. Blood Pressure Profiles

Group	Systolic BP (mmHg, Mean ± SD)	Diastolic BP (mmHg, Mean ± SD)	p-value
Normal Pregnancy	112.8 ± 8.2	73.4 ± 5.1	
Pre-Eclampsia	152.5 ± 11.6	101.7 ± 7.8	<0.001

Table 4. Correlation Between Blood Pressure and Serum Magnesium in the Pre-Eclampsia Group

Parameter	r-value	p-value
Magnesium vs Systolic BP	-0.61	<0.01
Magnesium vs Diastolic BP	-0.57	<0.01

Discussion

The present study identified a marked decline in maternal serum magnesium levels among women diagnosed with pre-eclampsia (mean = 1.72 mg/dL, SD = 0.19) when compared with normotensive pregnant participants (mean = 2.05 mg/dL, SD = 0.21), a difference that was highly significant (p < 0.001). This observed hypomagnesemia is consistent with findings from several recent investigations. For example, Rawal and Nayak (2025)¹² reported notably reduced magnesium concentrations in preeclamptic cases (1.82 ± 0.26 mg/dL) relative to healthy controls. Similarly, Boda et al. (2025)¹³ documented mean values of 1.79 ± 0.16 mg/dL and observed that a subset of women with magnesium levels below 1.6 mg/dL subsequently developed pre-eclampsia. Such concordance across studies strengthens the proposition that

decreased magnesium levels are significant biochemical marker in pre-eclamptic pregnancies. A contrasting outcome, however, was reported by Banu and Salina (2010) [14], who found slightly higher magnesium levels in women with eclampsia (0.847 ± 0.054 mmol/L; approximately 2.06 mg/dL) compared with those having pre-eclampsia (0.817 ± 0.489 mmol/L; ~1.99 mg/dL) and normotensive controls (0.815 ± 0.069 mmol/L; ~1.98 mg/dL). These differences may be explained by variations in demographic factors, nutritional background, timing of sample collection, and disease stage at the time of assessment. An important clinical consideration is that eclamptic patients are generally administered intravenous magnesium sulfate promptly after diagnosis as part of seizure

management. Elevated levels in their cohort could therefore reflect post-treatment supplementation rather than baseline physiological concentrations. In contrast, the present study as well as the recent works of Rawal and Nayak

¹² and Boda et al. ¹³ measured magnesium prior to any therapeutic intervention, thus capturing the untreated biochemical status associated with disease onset.

Notably, this study also demonstrated a moderate inverse correlation between serum magnesium concentration and both systolic and diastolic blood pressures ($r \approx -0.6$, $p < 0.01$) in the pre-eclampsia group. This relationship supports the biological plausibility that magnesium depletion may contribute to elevated vascular resistance and hypertension and also promotes unopposed calcium-driven vasoconstriction, all of which are recognised mechanisms in the development of pre-eclampsia¹⁵.

From a clinical perspective, the implications of magnesium deficiency are substantial. Beyond its diagnostic relevance as a potential biomarker, the therapeutic value of intravenous magnesium sulfate in preventing and treating eclamptic seizures is well established. The landmark Magpie Trial [¹⁶, ¹⁷] demonstrated a roughly 50% reduction in seizure incidence among treated patients, reinforcing its role as a cornerstone in pre-eclampsia management. Moreover, Boda et al.¹³ suggested that routine monitoring of serum magnesium could aid in predicting adverse maternal outcomes, although their findings on associations with preterm birth were not definitive.

In the Pakistani context, Aslam et al.¹⁸ conducted a comparative case-control study at Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur, to assess serum calcium and magnesium levels among mild pre-eclampsia (mPE), severe pre-eclampsia (sPE), and normotensive pregnant women. Their findings revealed a progressive decline in magnesium levels from normotensive controls (2.12 ± 0.22 mg/dL) to mPE (1.58 ± 0.42 mg/dL) and sPE (1.26 ± 0.44 mg/dL), with the reduction between mPE and sPE being highly significant ($p < 0.001$). While calcium levels were

also lower in pre-eclamptic groups, the difference between mPE and sPE was not statistically significant. The authors concluded that hypomagnesemia, more than hypocalcemia, could serve as a prognostic marker for disease severity. These results corroborate our study's observation that magnesium depletion is closely linked to the pathophysiology and progression of pre-eclampsia in the local population.

Limitations

This study was conducted at a single hospital with a relatively small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Dietary intake of magnesium and other nutritional factors was not assessed, and the cross-sectional design does not establish causality between low magnesium levels and pre-eclampsia.

Conclusion

This study found that women with pre-eclampsia had markedly lower serum magnesium levels (1.72 ± 0.19 mg/dL) compared to those with normal pregnancies (2.05 ± 0.21 mg/dL, $p < 0.001$). Blood pressure was significantly higher in the pre-eclampsia group, and magnesium levels showed a moderate negative correlation with both systolic and diastolic pressures.

Conflict of interest

The author states that there is no conflict of interest. This study is an independent study and it is not externally funded. It is undertaken as part of academics.

References

- Tavana Z, Hosseinmirzaei S. Comparison of maternal serum magnesium level in pre-eclampsia and normal pregnant women. *Iran Red Crescent Med J.* 2013;15(12):e10394-9.
- Sethi S, Kumari S, Sharma S, Batra N, Sharma A, Sharma R. A comparative study of serum calcium and magnesium levels in women with pre-eclampsia and normotensive women. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol.* 2021;10:2420-7.

- El-Maghraby GM, Zakarya MA, Hashish MA, El-Boghdady AA. Comparative study between serum calcium and magnesium levels in pre-eclampsia versus normal pregnancy. *Al-Azhar Med J.* 2022;51(2):999-1014.
- Winarno GNA, Pribadi A, Maruli HJ, Achmad ED, Anwar R, Mose JC, et al. Ratio of serum calcium to magnesium levels on pregnancy with and without preeclampsia. *Med Sci Monit.* 2021;27:e932032-37.
- Wadhvani N, Dangat K, Randhir K, Poddar A, Joshi P, Pisal H, et al. Longitudinal assessment of calcium and magnesium levels in women with preeclampsia. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2023;201(7):3245-55.
- Kumar TA, Keerthana BL, Lakshmi VB. Maternal serum calcium/magnesium ratio and electrolyte levels as biochemical predictors in hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. *J Med Sci.* 2025;11(1-4):1-6.
- Mondal C, Das D. High incidences of low serum magnesium in pre-eclampsia and eclampsia than in normal pregnancy. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2021;9(11):3302-3306.
- Tesfa E, Nibret E, Munshea A. Maternal serum zinc level and pre-eclampsia risk in African women: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2021;199(12):4564-71.
- Madendag Y, Sahin E, Madendag IC, Sahin ME, Kirlangic MM, Muhtaroglu S. Maternal serum telomerase levels increase in pregnancies with mild and severe preeclampsia. *Placenta.* 2022;123:41-5.
- Tosun S, Torun R, Kinci MF, Aksun S, Sengul M. Comparison of maternal serum neuropilin-1 (NRP-1) and fetal cord blood NRP-1 concentrations between normotensive pregnant women and those with preeclampsia. *J Clin Med.* 2025;14(11):3718-22.
- Mlay GH, Shayo PA, Kiritta RF, Matovelo DK, Kidenya BR. Strong association between hypocalcemia and preeclampsia-eclampsia among pregnant women attending a tertiary referral hospital in Northwestern Tanzania. *Sci Rep.* 2025;15(1):19151-57.
- Rawal PS, Nayak SR. Role of serum magnesium as predictor of preeclampsia. *J Obstet Gynaecol India.* 2025;:1-4.
- Boda R, Dabhadkar S, Taralekar V, Padwal MK, Takale LR. Evaluation of serum magnesium level and maternal outcomes in antenatal women. *JK Sci.* 2025;27(2):83-7.
- Banu S. Serum minerals levels in pre-eclampsia and eclampsia: association with clinical complications [PhD thesis]. Dhaka: University of Dhaka; 2025:1-20.
- Karabay G, Bayraktar B, Seyhanli Z, Tokgoz Cakir B, Aktemur G, Topkara Sucu S, et al. Evaluating maternal serum sortilin levels: a potential biomarker for predicting preeclampsia. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2025;25(1):1-9.
- Hou H, Lu Z, Zheng Y, Xu C, Wang L, Wang F. Associations of maternal serum transthyretin concentration with pregnancy and birth outcomes. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2025;25(1):503-8
- Tok A, Özer S, Özer A, Kaplanoğlu D, Arıkan T. An evaluation of serum boron level in pregnancies with severe pre-eclampsia. *Turk J Biochem.* 2025;50(2):297-303.
- Aslam F, Hayat I, Zakir FA, Haider SS, Nisa SU. Comparative analysis of serum calcium and magnesium as a better predictor in cases of mild and severe pre-eclampsia. *The Professional Medical Journal.* 2020 Aug 10;27(08):1722-7